

Stereodynamics of diheteroarylpiperidines and their derivatives[†]

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The stereodynamics of a number of *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-di(2-heteroaryl)- and *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-diarylpiperidines (12-17) have been studied. The conformational preferences have been correlated with those of *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-dimethylpiperidine (1) and *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-diphenylpiperidines (2a-f, 3a-e). Competition between $A^{1,3}$ -strain, torsional strain and 1,3-diaxial interaction appears to show varied influence on the ring geometry of all these *N*-nitrosopiperidines. Solution state conformational studies by NMR methods on *N*-nitroso compounds 12-17 reveal the preference of twist-boat conformation with a flattening at nitrogen end of the ring due to the coplanar nitroso group. The aryl substituents at C2 and C6 carbons are found to prefer pseudo-equatorial and pseudo-axial orientations, respectively. The semiempirical molecular orbital calculations, by using AM1 method, suggest the preference for twist-boat forms for 12-17. The X-ray diffraction studies on these *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones also confirm the preference for the non-chair conformations.

In *N*-nitrosopiperidines the delocalization of the lone-pair of electrons on the ring-nitrogen with the π -cloud of the *N*-substituent takes place and the ring-nitrogen attains a hybridization close to sp^2 leading to a bond angle of nearly 120° around nitrogen. Due to extensive delocalization¹ the N-N bond acquires partial double bond character which, in 2,6-disubstituted piperidines, results in a rotational equilibrium involving two rotamers (*syn* and *anti*, Fig. 1) with coplanar orientation of nitroso function (with respect to C6-

Fig. 1. Equilibrium involving *syn* and *anti* rotamers.

N1-C2 plane). The barrier for N-N rotation was found to be 81.2 kJ mol^{-1} for *N*-nitroso-*cis-2,6*-dimethylpiperidine^{2a}. If the substituents at α -positions of the sp^2 centres occupy equatorial orientations, they exhibit a severe nonbonded interaction (known as $A^{1,3}$ -strain)^{3,4} with the coplanar -N=N=O function which is larger than that can arise when the substituents are 1,3-diaxially related. In the case of *N*-nitroso-*cis-2,6*-dimethylpiperidine (1) the methyl groups are forced to occupy the axial orientation in order to avoid the $A^{1,3}$ -strain and an equilibrium exists between the two coplanar orientations (*syn* and *anti*) of the nitroso function⁵.

On the other hand, we found that the *N*-nitroso-*cis-2,6*-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones (2a-f) and *N*-nitroso-2,6-diphenylpiperidines^{6,7} (3a-e) prefer, in solid state, twist-boat conformations, while in solution, twist-chair conformations with pseudoaxial orientations of α -substituents and pseudoequatorial orientations of β -alkyl substituents. The 3-isopropyl-*N*-nitroso-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (4), in solid state, was found to prefer an alternate chair conformation in which all the ring substituents occupy axial orientations^{6c,8}. In all the cases, the nitroso group was found to adopt coplanar orientations^{6,7} and the interaction between the phenyl groups and the N-N=O function appears to be critical in determining the preferred conformations.

Due to the restricted rotation around N-N bond these nitrosamines exist in equilibrium between the two rotamers, *syn* and *anti*. The N-N rotational barriers for the nitrosamines 2a, 2e, 2f and 3a, determined from dynamic NMR spectral studies, were found to be 80.8, 80.0, 77.0 and 75.8 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively⁶. Since the effects of heteroaryl substituents, such as thienyl and furyl, on the $A^{1,3}$ -strain and other interactions are not known, we prepared three new *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-di(2-heteroaryl)piperidin-4-ones (12-14) and examined their conformations. A few *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-diarylpiperidin-4-ones (15-17) were also prepared.

Results and Discussion

The *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17) were obtained from the corresponding piperidin-4-ones (6-11) by nitrosation using nitrous acid (Scheme 1) as described earlier^{6a}. The preferred conformations of these *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones were found to be twist-boat with a coplanar orientation of N-N=O function, thereby leading to a conformational equilibrium between *syn* and *anti* rotamers. The substituents at C2 and C3 were found to adopt pseudo-equatorial orientations while those at C5 and C6

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on his 75th. birth anniversary.

preferred pseudo-axial orientations.

Stereochemical analysis of the heteroaryl piperidin-4-ones (6-11) using NMR spectral methods indicates, as anticipated, the preference for a chair conformation with equatorial substituents^{9,11,12}. Moreover, the X-ray diffraction studies^{9,10} also indicate the preference for chair conformations with the hetero atom of the heteroaryl ring forcing the aryl moiety to drift further away from the nitrogen-end of the piperidine ring.

Scheme 1. Preparation of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (6-11).

Preferred conformations of the N-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17) :

Each of the protons and carbons of the *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17) showed two signals in the ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra. For example, *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-di(2-thienyl)-*t-3,t-5*-dimethylpiperidin-4-one (13) showed two doublets at δ 1.05 and 1.25 ppm for methyl groups at C3 and C5, two doublets of quartets at δ 3.33 and 3.44 ppm for methine protons (H3 and H5), two doublets at δ 5.61 and

6.28 ppm for benzylic protons (H2 and H6). Similar to earlier cases^{6,7}, the doubling of ¹H and ¹³C NMR signals in these *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17) was found to be due to N-N rotational equilibria between two conformations with coplanar orientation of nitroso function. In *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones 12-17, the α -carbons were found to be shielded compared to their parent compounds (6-11) (Table 1). One of the two α -carbons was shifted upfield by 5-6 ppm and the other by 7-10 ppm, showing that the nitroso group is coplanar to the C2-N-C6 plane of the piperidine ring causing gamma-eclipsing interactions between the N-O and N-C α bonds^{13,14}. Though both the α -protons H2 and H6 (as well as β -protons H3 and H5) in the nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17) were deshielded compared to those in the piperidin-4-ones (6-11), the degree of deshielding for one of the α - (as well as β) protons (δ 2.5 ppm) was larger than the other (δ 1.5 ppm). Such a large difference in the degree of deshielding/shielding of α - and β -protons or carbons can be related to the coplanar orientation only. Hence the possibility of equilibrium between the conformers IA-IB was ruled out (Fig. 2).

Ring reversal (IIA-IIIA/IIB-IIIB and VA-VIA/VB-VIB) :

Since the orientation of the nitroso group is coplanar, the equilibrium between IIA-IIIA and IIB-IIIB or VA-VIA and VB-VIB will lead to four NMR absorptions for each proton, i.e. two NMR absorptions for *syn* and *anti* rotamers of one chair/boat form and two for the other chair/boat form. All these compounds, however, showed only two NMR signals.

Hence it may be stated that there cannot be more than two energetically distinguishable conformers (or rotamers) in equilibrium at 25°. If any contribution from a third ener-

Table 1. ¹³C NMR chemical shifts (δ ppm) of α - and β -carbons of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones 12-17 and piperidin-4-ones 6-11

Compd. no.	C-2		C-6		C-3		C-5	
	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>
12	53.75	61.12	-	-	43.42	45.06	-	-
6		61.13				49.65		
13	55.85	62.97	-	-	46.25	47.45	-	-
7		63.53				53.04		
14	55.58	63.25	48.08	56.67	46.95	48.08	42.26	43.20
8		63.38		56.56		52.83		51.27
15	58.22	59.02	-	-	46.46	47.24	-	-
9		62.59				52.07		
16	56.09	62.60	-	-	45.63	46.62	-	-
10		62.70				51.50		
17	61.80	65.99	-	-	44.76	45.42	-	-
11		68.90				51.82		

decrease of coupling constants revealed the unsymmetrical twisting of the piperidine ring along C3-C2-N1-C6-C5 linkage.

On the basis of the unequal vicinal coupling constants and other NMR data it was concluded that among the six proposed pairs of rotamers those with twist-boat (IVA-IVB) (Fig. 3) conformation were preferred.

Fig 3. Conformational equilibrium between the *syn* and *anti* rotamers of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones 12-17.

Assignment of ¹H and ¹³C NMR signals to syn and anti rotamers :

In order to understand the preferred conformations of the individual rotamers (Fig. 3) the identification of the NMR signals corresponding to *syn* and *anti* rotamers was necessary. The coplanar nitroso group caused the anisotropic deshielding of α - and β -protons corresponding to *syn* and *anti* rotamers in the *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17). According to the model proposed by Paulsen and Todt¹⁵, the protons which lie within the N-N=O plane will appear in the downfield region compared to those which are away from the plane. The assignment of *syn* and *anti* signals could be better achieved by means of HETCOR studies.

HETCOR spectra :

¹H-¹³C HETCOR spectra were employed for the unambiguous assignment of *syn* and *anti* NMR signals. This method is based on the observation that the carbons *syn* to X=Y functions, in compounds containing N-X=Y functions such as NNO, NCOR, etc., are always more shielded than the *anti*^{16,14}. Between the two benzylic ¹³C signals at δ 53.75 and 61.12 ppm observed in the HETCOR spectrum of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-one 12, the one at upfield region (δ 53.75 ppm) was assigned to the carbon *syn* to the nitroso group and that at δ 61.12 ppm assigned to that *anti* to nitroso group. Since these two carbon signals δ 53.75 and 61.12 ppm correlated with the benzylic doublets at δ 5.47 and 6.22 ppm, respectively, the former signal was assigned to α -proton *syn* to nitroso group and the latter at δ 6.22 ppm to the *anti* α -proton. The same method of assignments has been extended to other protons of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-one 12 also. Similar assignments were made for *N*-nitrosamines 13-16 also using the HETCOR spectra.

¹H NMR signals : Influence of nitroso function on the α - and β -protons :

α -Protons : The magnitude of shielding or deshielding

Table 3. Vicinal coupling constants of α - and β -protons in *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (12-17)*

Compd. no.	$J^3_{2a,3a}$		$J^3_{5a,6a}$	
	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>
12	9.5	3.3	-	-
6	(10.8)		-	-
13	9.7	3.5	-	-
7	(10.2)		-	-
14	9.0	5.4	6.6	2.5
8	(10.2)		(11.7, 3.4)	
15	9.0	5.0	-	-
9	(10.4)		-	-
16	9.2	3.6	-	-
10	(10.1)		-	-
17	10.2	3.4	-	-
11	(10.2)		-	-

*Values in parentheses correspond to the parent piperidin-4-ones 12-17.

of the α - and β -protons in *N*-nitrosamines with reference to the protons in the parent amines, may be expected to depend upon their relative orientations with respect to N-N=O plane. The orientations of the protons in turn depend upon the local conformation of the molecule. As pointed out earlier according to the model proposed by Paulsen and Todt¹⁵ to explain amide anisotropy, if the protons lie within the N-N=O plane (in-plane region) those *syn* to the nitroso group are deshielded more than the *anti*. On the other hand, if they are away from the N-N=O plane (out-of-plane region) the *syn* protons are less deshielded (or shielded) than the *anti*.

A comparison of chemical shifts of α -(H2 and H6) and β -(H3 and H5) protons in *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones 12-17 with those of the corresponding parent piperidin-4-ones 6-11 revealed that both the α - and β -protons have experienced downfield shifts (Table 4) irrespective of whether they are *syn* or *anti* to the nitroso group. In each of the *N*-nitrosamines, out of the two α -proton signals, the one which had experienced higher deshielding compared to its counterpart was considered to be *anti* to nitroso group (Table 4). For instance, in the case of the *N*-nitroso compound 13 the signal at δ 5.61 ppm was assigned to the H2-*syn* (or H6-*syn*) protons and that at δ 6.28 ppm to H2-*anti* (or H6-*anti*).

Although the β -protons (H3 and H5) showed low magnetic anisotropy than α -(H2 and H6), the magnitudes of deshielding or shielding encountered by these protons were significantly different from those of the parent amines. Both the *syn* and *anti* β -protons were deshielded in the *N*-nitrosamines 12, 13, 14 and 17. In the case of the *cis-r-2,c-6-di-*

Table 4 Nitroso induced ¹H NMR chemical shifts of α , β , Γ protons in *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones (**12-14**, **16-17**)

Compd no	H2		H6		H3		H5		C3(Me)/C5(Me)	
	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>
12	+1 72	+2 47	–	–	+0 38	+0 51	–	–	+0 09	+0 34
13	+1 66	+2 33	–	–	+0 59	+0 70	–	–	+0 14	+0 35
14	+1 72	+2 63	+1 93	+2 46	+0 61	+0 84	+0 7	0 0	+0 95	+0 30
16	+1 23	+2 12	–	–	+1 56	+1 14	–	–	+0 20	+0 32
17	+1 66	+2 58	–	–	+0 29	+0 71	–	–	+0 10	+0 36

o-chlorophenyl and *o*-methoxyphenyl substituted *N*-nitrosamines **15** and **16**, one of the β -protons was shielded while the other deshielded. For instance, in *N*-nitroso-*r*-2, *c*-6-di-*o*-methoxyphenyl-*t*-3, *t*-5-dimethylpiperidin-4-one (**16**) the *anti* β -proton (δ 3.06 ppm) was shielded and the *syn* β -proton was deshielded. This shielding of *anti* β -protons in nitrosamines **15** and **16** suggested an ‘out-of-plane’ orientation for these protons and ‘in-plane’ orientation of *syn* β -protons (H3). The preferred ‘out-of-plane’ orientation of *anti* β -protons in **15** and **16** may be due to the twist along C2-C3 leading to a possible through space interaction between the *ortho*-substituents (*o*-OMe, *o*-Cl) of the phenyl group at C5 and the H5 proton.

The twist along C2-C3 in *N*-nitrosamines **15-16** was further supported by the relatively lower vicinal coupling exhibited by the *anti* β -proton H5 than that exhibited by the *syn*.

Aromatic protons : In *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **12-17** the aromatic protons were shielded by 0.2–0.3 ppm compared to their parent piperidin-4-ones **6-11** irrespective of whether the nitroso group was *syn* or *anti*. Though the shifts are very low they may be attributed to the repulsive effect operating between the nitroso π -cloud and the aromatic π -cloud. For instance, in piperidin-4-one **6** the aromatic signals appeared around δ 6.27–7.38 ppm whereas in its *N*-nitroso analog **12** the aromatic signals were around δ 6.06–7.14 ppm for *syn* and δ 6.12–7.38 ppm for *anti*. The repulsion was considered to be high when nitroso group was oriented *syn* to the aromatic ring and less when oriented *anti* to the aromatic ring.

¹³C NMR signals The influence of nitroso function on α - and β -carbons :

In *N*-nitroso compounds **12-17** both the *syn* and *anti* α - and β -carbons were shielded compared to their parent compounds **6-11** (Table 5). The magnitude of shielding was higher (\approx 7.0 ppm) for the *syn* α -carbons than the *anti* α -carbons (0.5–2.0 ppm). The higher shielding of the *syn* carbon may be attributed to the eclipsing interaction between the N–O bond of the nitroso group and the N1–C2 bond.

Table 5 ¹³C NMR chemical shifts induced by *N*-nitroso function on α - and β -carbons of the *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **6-11** with respect to their parent piperidin-4-ones

Compd no	C2		C6		C3		C5	
	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>	<i>syn</i>	<i>anti</i>
12	–7 38	–0 01	–	–	–6 23	–4 59	–	–
13	–7 68	–0 56	–	–	–6 79	–5 59	–	–
14	–7 80	–0 13	–8 48	–0 11	–5 88	–4 75	–9 01	–8 07
15	–4 37	–3 54	–	–	–5 61	–4 83	–	–
16	–6 80	–2 70	–	–	–6 90	–5 90	–	–
17	–7 10	–2 91	–	–	–7 04	–6 38	–	–

The *syn* and *anti* β -carbons (C3 and C5) were shielded by around 5–6 ppm in nitroso compounds **12-17** with respect to their parent amines **6-11**. The shielding of the β -carbon may arise due to the gamma-anti-effect produced by the N–N bond on these carbons.

Ipsso and aromatic carbons : The *ipso* carbons in nitrosamines **12-17** were shielded by \approx 4–5 ppm compared to their corresponding parent compounds **6-11**. This shielding may be rationalized by the gamma-*gauche* interaction between N(1)–N(2) and the C α -C*ipso* carbons. The aromatic carbons were shielded by 2–3 ppm due to π - π repulsion between the aromatic ring and nitroso function. Thus the solution state conformational studies on *N*-nitroso compounds **12-17** revealed the preference of twist-boat conformation for these compounds with a flattening at nitrogen end of the ring due to the coplanar nitroso group. The aryl substituents at C6 and C2 carbons were found to prefer pseudo-equatorial and pseudo-axial orientations, respectively.

The preferred conformations of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **12**, **15** and **16** in the solid state were determined by X-ray diffraction methods⁹. The torsional angles of $-6.0(6)^\circ$ and $-171.3(4)^\circ$ for C2–N1–N20–O21 and C6–N1–N20–O21 in nitrosamine **12**, $-9.5(2)^\circ$ and $-169.0(2)^\circ$ in nitrosamine **15**, and $-4.1(1)^\circ$ and $-171.7(1)^\circ$ in nitrosamine **16**, respectively, showed the existence of coplanar orientation of the nitroso group in the solid state also.

The dihedral angle of $157.8(2)^\circ$ for C8–C5–C6–C9 in **12**

indicated that the furyl and methyl groups at C6 and C5 were almost *anti* to each other adopting pseudo-axial orientations. In contrast the dihedral angle of $-64.7(2)^\circ$ for C1-C2-C3-C7 showed pseudo-equatorial orientations for C2 furyl and C3 methyl groups and were found to be *gauche* to one another. In addition, these dihedral angles supported the higher vicinal coupling constants between H2 and H3 protons which are *syn* to nitroso function as well as the lower coupling constants between H5 and H6 protons (*anti* to nitroso group). In contrast, the parent piperidin-4-ones **6** and **7** showed the dihedral angles of $-62.4 \pm 3.0^\circ$ and $58.5 \pm 1.0^\circ$ for C8-C5-C6-C9 and C14-C2-C3-C7, respectively, indicating the equatorial orientations for the ring substituents at C2, C3, C5 and C6 carbons^{9b}.

In *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **12** and **15** the methyl group at C3 occupies an equatorial orientation which was inferred from the torsional angle of $\approx 168.0^\circ$ for N1-C2-C3-C7 and the other methyl group at C5 occupies axial orientation as evidenced from the torsional angle of $\approx -72.0^\circ$ for N1-C6-C5-C8. The influence of the lone-pair-lone-pair repulsion between the heteroatom of the aryl moiety with nitroso oxygen can be observed from the increase in dihedral angle N1-C2-C-O15 from 56.54° in parent piperidin-4-one **6** to 59.50° in *N*-nitroso derivative **12**. Thus the solid state conformations of **12** and **15** were confirmed as twist-boat with coplanar nitroso orientations with the substituents in the pseudo-axial and pseudo-equatorial position in order to alleviate the A^{1,3}-strain, eclipsing interactions and bond opposition strains.

Stereodynamics of N-nitroso-2,6-diheteroarylpiperidin-4-ones and N-nitroso-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones. Dynamic NMR studies :

As indicated in the earlier sections, the ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **12-17** exhibited a well resolved pair of NMR absorptions for each proton and carbon at room temperature. A detailed analysis of the NMR spectra revealed that the orientation of the nitroso group was coplanar and the equilibrium between the *syn* and *anti* rotamers was due to the N-N restricted rotation.

The rotational barriers for N-N rotation of four *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones were calculated from dynamic ¹H NMR spectra (Chart 1) using Eyring equation²⁰. *N*-Nitrosopiperidin-4-ones **12** and **13** showed rotational barriers of 80.5 and 73.7 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively, for N-N bond rotation. The corresponding barrier for its phenyl substituted analog **2e** was reported to be 80.2 kJ mol⁻¹. While the barrier for nitrosamine **12** was almost the same as that of **2e**, the barrier for N-N rotation in nitroso compound **13** was reduced by 6.5 kJ mol⁻¹. The decrease in the barrier for

Chart 1. Dynamic ¹H NMR spectra of **12**

the *N*-nitroso-2,6-dithienylpiperidin-4-one **13** may be attributed to its ground state destabilisation arising due to the

Table 6. Rotational barriers of *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-ones with varying substituents

Compd. no.	Rotational barriers kJ mol ⁻¹	Ref
NDM ^a	96.2	1
NP ^b	93.0	17
NDMP ^c	81.2	5
NTMP ^d	82.3	2b
2a	80.8	6
2e	80.0	6
2f	77.0	6
3a	75.8	6
12	80.5	*
13	73.7	*
16	70.3	*
17	80.7	*

^a*N,N*-Dimethylnitrosamine.

^b*N*-Nitrosopiperidine

^c*N*-Nitroso-2,6-dimethylpiperidine.

^d*N*-Nitroso-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine.

* = Present work.

lone-pair–lone-pair repulsion between the sulfur atom in thienyl ring and the nitroso oxygen.

The influence of different substituents with varying bulkiness on the N–N rotational barrier is given in Table 6. For example, *N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-one without any ring substituents had a rotational barrier of 93.5 kJ mol⁻¹ (Ref. 17). On introducing methyl groups at C2 and C6 positions, the ΔG^\ddagger value was reduced (to 81.2 kJ mol⁻¹) by ≈ 11.0 kJ mol⁻¹. In *N*-nitroso-2,6-dimethylpiperidine (**1**), due to the A^{1,3}-strain both the methyl groups at C2 and C6 preferred to occupy axial orientations. The resulting 1,3-diaxial interaction may partly destabilize the ground state conformation of this compound and hence ΔG^\ddagger was reduced. When the phenyl groups were introduced at C2 and C6 positions instead of methyl groups, the energy barrier was found to be lowered further ($\Delta G^\ddagger = 80.0$) by 1.2 kJ mol⁻¹.

Semiempirical calculations :

The stereochemical preferences of *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-di(2-heteroaryl)-piperidines **12–14** and *N*-nitroso-*cis-r-2,c-6*-diarylpiperidines **15–17** were calculated by the AM1

Fig. 4

Table 7. Calculated relative formation energies (kcal mol⁻¹) of various conformers* of *N*-nitrosopiperidines **12–17** by AM1 method

Compd. no.		CE	CA	B1	Conformer	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6
					ΔH_f (calcd.)					
12	<i>syn</i>	2.49	3.37	0.00	-9.47	1.30	–	–	–	–
	<i>anti</i>	2.49	3.37	1.30		0.00	–	–	–	–
13	<i>syn</i>	7.09	5.32	0.60	34.76	0.00	–	–	5.84	7.75
	<i>anti</i>	7.09	5.32	0.00		0.60	–	–	5.47	7.81
14	<i>syn</i>	7.18	5.15	0.00	37.32	1.24	–	–	–	9.35
	<i>anti</i>	7.01	5.17	0.49		1.78	–	–	–	–
15	<i>syn</i>	1.81	1.89	1.15	21.35	1.72	2.75	0.70	–	–
	<i>anti</i>	1.38	1.83	0.73		1.91	0.00	7.07	–	–
16	<i>syn</i>	2.58	2.14	0.44	-45.34	1.23	2.92	0.00	–	–
	<i>anti</i>	2.58	2.14	1.23		0.44	0.00	2.92	–	–
17	<i>syn</i>	3.79	1.70	0.00	-188.76	2.84	–	1.29	4.78	–
	<i>anti</i>	3.75	2.15	1.70		0.86	1.71	3.91	5.03	4.16

*Though all the conformations were considered for optimization some of them were not found to be stable and they instantly converted into other forms.

method of MOPAC package²¹ (Version 6.00). All calculations were performed on a Pentium personal computer using the keywords AM1 PRECISE EF GNORM = 0.1. Table 7 shows the relative formation energies of the conformers corresponding to the calculated energy minima along with the calculated heat of formation (ΔH_f) for the global minimum conformation of the compound. As in the case of spectral studies all the possible conformations of the nitrosopiperidines has been considered, viz. two chair conformations **CE**, **CA** and six boat conformations **B1–B6** (Fig. 4). Every possible mode of conformational changes arising

out of rotations, ring flipping, etc., have been considered by periodically changing the selected dihedral angles with and without constraints. The absence of chair and boat conformations with equatorial α -substituents (**CE** and **B6**) as the preferred conformers indicates the dominant role of A^{1,3}-strain over other steric factors in deciding the most stable conformer of the compound.

The results obtained by changing the torsional angle C2–N1–N–O in every one of the forms point out the preference of the coplanar orientation of nitroso function with respect to the C2–N1–C6 plane of the ring. The presence of partial

double bond character in N–N bond of the *N*-nitroso function and the change in the bond angle around N1 nitrogen towards the sp^2 hybridization were also observed. In the case of *N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-heteroaryl)piperidin-4-ones 12–14 and diarylpiperidin-4-one 17 the B1 conformation was found to be the most preferred geometry while the other two diarylpiperidin-4-ones 15 and 16 prefer the B3 conformation. The AM1 optimized structures of 2,6-di(*o*-chlorophenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-*N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-one (15) has been given as representative example (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. AM1 optimized structures of 15.

Thus the introduction of the nitroso function in piperidin-4-ones 6–11 results in the change in conformation from chair to twist-boat conformations. Though the heteroatom in the aryl substituents did not seem to cause any significant impact on the overall conformation of the piperidine ring, it influences the orientation of the heteroaryl ring in such a way that the hetero atom stayed away from the nitroso oxygen.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer (70 eV). ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$) were recorded on Varian XL-300, Bruker MSL-300 or Jeol GSX-400 MHz instruments. Dynamic ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker-270 MHz instrument as $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ solutions and

low temperature studies were carried out in CDCl_3 solution using a Jeol GSX (400 MHz) instrument. The chemical shift difference at T_c was determined by extrapolating the plot of temperature against the chemical shift difference. Free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) was calculated by using the modified Eyring equation for compounds 12–13 and 16–17. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigens). The piperidin-4-ones 6–8 and 11 were prepared by following the literature procedure¹⁸ with slight modification. A representative procedure is given for compound 6. All nitrosations were performed as reported earlier^{6a}.

r-2,*c*-6-Di(2-furyl)-*t*-3,*t*-5-dimethylpiperidin-4-one (6) : To a solution of ammonium acetate (7.7 g, 100 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml), pentan-3-one (10.0 ml, 100 mmol) and furfuraldehyde (16.5 ml, 200 mmol) were added and the solution was kept under reflux for 1 h and then allowed to cool. To the cooled reaction mixture, diethyl ether (250 ml) saturated with HCl gas added in portions when the corresponding hydrochloride of *r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-furyl)-*t*-3, *t*-5-dimethylpiperidin-4-one 6a precipitated out. The hydrochloride 6a was filtered, washed with minimum quantity of ether-ethanol mixture (4 : 1), dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , suspended in acetone (15 ml) and neutralized using ammonia solution (2.0 ml). The clear solution obtained was poured in ice-cold water (100 ml). The solid separated was dried and recrystallised from ethanol as colorless diamond-like crystals (5.0 g, 9.7%), m.p. 69–71° (Found : C, 69.71; H, 6.46; N, 5.58. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$ calcd. for : C, 69.48; H, 6.00; N, 5.40%); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 0.91 (d, CH_3), 2.25 (s br, NH), 2.94 (m, H3, H5), 3.75 (dd, H2, H6), 6.27–7.38 (ArH); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ 10.5 (CH_3), 49.7 (C3, C5), 61.1 (C2, C6), 107.4, 110.1, 142.1, 153.6 (aromatic carbons), 209.7 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-thienyl)piperidin-4-one (7) : Yield 15.4%, m.p. 100–102° (Found : C, 62.04; H, 5.59; N, 4.98; S, 21.86. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{NS}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : C, 61.82; H, 5.87; N, 4.80; S, 22.00%); ^1H NMR δ 0.9 (d, Me), 2.5 (s br, NH), 2.74 (m, C3, C5), 3.95 (d, C2, C6), 6.92–7.0 (m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR δ 10.47 (CH_3), 53.0 (C3, C5), 63.5 (C2, C6), 125.0, 126.1, 145.4 (aromatic carbons), 209.3 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3-Methyl-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-thienyl)piperidin-4-one (8) : Yield 12.5%, m.p. 49–52° (Found : C, 60.44; H, 5.57; N, 5.16; S, 23.23. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{NS}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for : C, 60.61; H, 5.45; N, 5.05; S, 23.11%); ^1H NMR δ 0.92 (d, CH_3), 2.48 (s br, NH), 2.71 (m, H3, H5), 3.98 (d, H2/H6), 4.40 (dd, H2/H6), 6.94–7.29 (m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR δ 10.2 (CH_3), 51.3

(C5), 52.83 (C3), 56.53 (C6), 63.38 (C2), 123.7, 124.60, 125.1, 125.2, 126.5, 145.2, 146.03 (aromatic carbons), 207.7 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-piperidin-4-one (**11**) : Yield 16.7%, m.p. 138–139° (Found : C, 65.51; H, 7.35; N, 3.11. C₂₅H₃₃NO₇ calcd. for : C, 65.34; H, 7.24; N, 3.05%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.87 (d, CH₃), 2.1 (s br, NH), 2.75 (m, H3, H5), 3.51 (d, H2, H6), 3.83–3.88 (s, O-Me), 6.58–6.71 (ArH); ¹³C NMR δ 10.4 (CH₃), 51.8 (C3/C5), 68.9 (C2/C6), 55.9, 60.6 (OMe's), 104.4, 137.3, 137.4, 152.96 (aromatic carbons), 210.56 (carbonyl carbon).

r-2,*c*-6-Di(2-furyl)-*t*-3,*t*-5-dimethyl-*N*-nitrosopiperidin-4-one (**12**) : Yield 52%, m.p. 96–98° (Found : C, 62.73; H, 5.38; N, 9.86. C₁₅H₁₆N₂O₄ calcd. For : C, 62.49; H, 5.59; N, 9.70%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 1.00 (d, Me), 3.32 (m, H3, H5), 5.47 (d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H2, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.25 (d, Me), 3.45 (m, H3, H5), 6.22 (d, *J* 3.3 Hz, H2, H6), 6.31–7.71 (ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 12.6 (Me), 43.4 (C3, C5), 53.75 (C2, C6); *anti*-conformer : 15.3 (Me), 45.1 (C3, C5), 61.1 (C2, C6); 109.2, 110.4, 110.9, 141.7, 143.1 (aromatic carbons), 149.0, 150.0 (*ipso*-carbons).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-thienyl)piperidin-4-one (**13**) : Yield 47%, m.p. 101–102° (Found : C, 56.61; H, 5.06; N, 8.38; S, 20.21. C₁₅H₁₆N₂S₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 56.22; H, 5.03; N, 8.74; S, 20.01%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 1.05 (d, Me), 3.33 (m, H3, H5), 5.61 (d, *J* 9.7 Hz, H2, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.26 (d, Me), 3.44 (m, H3, H5), 6.28 (d, *J* 3.5 Hz, H2, H6), 6.74–7.36 (aromatic protons corresponding to both *syn* and *anti* conformers); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 13.0 (Me), 46.3 (C3, C5), 55.85 (C2, C6); *anti*-conformer : 15.6 (Me), 47.5 (C3, C5), 62.97 (C2, C6); 125.6, 126.4, 126.9, 127.1, 127.2, 127.4 (aromatic carbons), 140.3, 142.1 (*ipso*-carbons), 208.1 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3-Methyl-*N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(2-thienyl)piperidin-4-one (**14**) : Yield 24%, m.p. 62–65° (Found : C, 54.67; H, 4.32; N, 9.44; S, 20.67. C₁₄H₁₄N₂S₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 54.88; H, 4.60; N, 9.14; S, 20.93%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 1.07 (d, Me), 3.22 (m, H3, H5), 5.70 (d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H2), 6.30 (d, *J* 5.4 Hz, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.22 (d, Me), 3.45 (m, H3, H5), 6.16 (d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H2), 6.81 (d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H6), 6.9–7.6 (aromatic protons corresponding to both *syn* and *anti* conformers); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 13.4 (Me), 42.26 (C5), 47.0 (C3), 48.1 (C6), 55.6 (C2); *anti*-conformer : 14.8 (Me), 43.21 (C5), 48.1 (C3), 56.7 (C6), 63.3 (C2); 125.6, 125.7, 126.3, 126.5, 126.8, 127.0, 127.1,

127.3 (aromatic carbons), 140.0, 140.1, 140.2 (*ipso*-carbons), 205.7, 206.5 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(*o*-chlorophenyl)-piperidin-4-one (**15**) : Yield 52%, m.p. 158–161° (Found : C, 60.70; H, 4.72; N, 7.68; Cl, 18.63. C₁₉H₁₈Cl₂N₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 60.49; H, 4.81; N, 7.42; Cl, 18.79%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 1.12 (d, Me), 3.46 (m, H3, H5), 5.58 (d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H2, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.24 (d, Me), 3.04 (m, H3, H5), 6.47 (d, *J* 5.0 Hz, H2, H6), 6.27–7.58 (aromatic protons corresponding to both *syn* and *anti* conformers); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 13.1 (Me), 46.5 (C3, C5), 58.2 (C2, C6); *anti*-conformer : 15.5 (Me), 47.2 (C3, C5), 59.0 (C2, C6); 124.9, 125.7, 127.4, 127.6, 128.4, 128.9, 130.0, 130.5, 131.2 (aromatic carbons), 134.1, 135.1, 135.9, 137.0 (*ipso*-carbons), 209.4 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(*o*-methoxyphenyl)piperidin-4-one (**16**) : Yield 60%, m.p. 173–175° (Found : C, 68.70; H, 5.42; N, 7.74. C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 68.46; H, 6.56; N, 7.60%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 1.03 (d, Me), 3.50 (m, H3, H5), 3.77 (s, OMe), 5.62 (d, *J* 9.2 Hz, H2, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.18 (d, Me), 3.06 (m, H3, H5), 3.38 (s, OMe), 6.29 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, H2, H6), 6.32–7.44 (aromatic protons corresponding to both *syn* and *anti* conformers); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 13.1 (Me), 45.6 (C3, C5), 56.1 (C2, C6), 55.5 (OMe); *anti*-conformer : 15.6 (Me), 46.6 (C3, C5), 62.6 (C2, C6), 55.7 (OMe); 110.9, 111.7, 120.6, 120.9, 125.7, 125.8, 127.1, 128.7, 128.9, 130.5 (aromatic carbons), 157.0, 158.7 (*ipso*-carbons), 210.0 (carbonyl carbon).

t-3,*t*-5-Dimethyl-*N*-nitroso-*r*-2,*c*-6-di(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)piperidin-4-one (**17**) : Yield 49%, m.p. 181–183° (Found : C, 61.69; H, 6.51; N, 5.87. C₂₅H₃₂N₂O₈ calcd. for : C, 61.46; H, 6.60; N, 5.73%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 0.97 (d, Me), 3.04 (m, H3, H5), 5.17 (d, *J* 10.2 Hz, H2, H6); *anti*-conformer : 1.23 (d, Me), 3.46 (m, H3, H5), 6.09 (d, *J* 3.4 Hz, H2, H6), 3.66, 3.78, 3.79, 3.84 (4s, OMe), 6.10–7.28 (ArH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ *syn*-conformer : 12.5 (Me), 44.8 (C3, C5), 61.8 (C2, C6); *anti*-conformer : 15.7 (Me), 45.4 (C3, C5), 66.0 (C2, C6), 55.9, 55.92, 56.2, 56.3, 60.7 (OMe carbons), 104.6, 104.9, 133.2, 133.8, 137.4, 138.1 (aromatic carbons), 153.1, 153.6 (*ipso*-carbons), 209.4 (carbonyl carbon).

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